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ENERGY EFFICIENT OPTICAL CHARACTER RECOGNITION (OCR) BASED SMART VEHICLE AUTHENTICATION & ACCESS CONTROL SYSTEM

Dr. Himanshu Monga

Professor & Assoc. Dean

Lovely Professional University, Jalandhar, INDIA

Abstract:

The proposed system can heighten supervision as well as proficiency of an Authentication and Access Control System. In today's world, all individuals utilize diverse forms of security goods in their factories, workplaces and households. For instance, video recorders, cameras, sensors, GSM, and alarm centered security networks. This project can be used at entrance of any secure area where ever we need high security to control the access of confidential vehicles only. The various modules of the project will be webcam installed with PC, Microcontroller unit, Line driver (MAX232), Display unit (LCD) which can be monitored by some authenticated person, isolation & amplifier circuit and stepper motor to open or close the entry gate and to turn street light.

Index terms-Optical Characters Recognition (OCR), Image Processing, Security System, Access Control System, Power Saving, Energy Efficiency, ZigBee.

I. INTRODUCTION

The idea in this project is to let some specific authenticated vehicles and persons to pass in a particular area of any organization. Employment of this scheme could be in army regions where only certain army officials can enter and noncombatants are not permissible to enter. Once a person or vehicle is allowed to enter, as the gate opens it will turn on street light because street lighting is always required at night.

Lighting systems are still constructed in agreement with the longstanding principles or dependability, plus they habitually do not take benefit of latest technological improvements. In

many cases it associated with the plant supervisors who haven't concluded the yield of the expenditures derived from the production of prevailing facilities yet. Nevertheless, the latest accumulative pressure linked to the raw material prices and the larger social compassion to ecological matters and several concerns linked to security are leading builders to obtain new practices and technologies that allows significant cost savings and a greater respect to the environment and most important factor security. We can find three possible solutions to these problems in the literature.

The initial one and possibly the utmost instinctive is the use of new technologies for the sources of light such as light emitting diodes. [1][2] have already considered this possibility.

The second possible solution and perhaps most revolutionary, is to use street lighting and gate security system together. It will reduce raw material and as well as cost of the overall system.

Finally the third possibility would be use of renewable energy sources locally available, rather than conventional power sources, with positive effect on environment.

II. DEVICES AND METHODS

Fig.1 illustrates the theoretical schematic of the proposed network.

Every time an automobile or an individual approaches at the entry gate, the web cam positioned in the processor takes the picture of number plate of the vehicle. After the image is captured, the MATLAB code implanted in the computer processor processes this image to identify the number on the number plate via Optical Character Recognition technology. After identifying the number, MATLAB code matches this number with the pre-stored databank. If this info matches with the database of the computer then a number "a" is send to microcontroller that is attached along the other side of computer or else, a number "b" is send to the microcontroller. Stepper motor is permitted to open the entry gate if the number "a" is received by MCU & that vehicle or person is permitted to pass.

It basically consists of two parts, first is gate security system and second is street lighting.

1. SECURTY SYSTEM

i) Microcontroller PIC 16F877 Series: Microcontroller Unit is the heart of our project. It controls all the major activities of our project. The Microcontroller unit used in our project is based on PIC family. This microcontroller is a 40-pin device and is one of the popular

microcontrollers used in complex applications. The device offers 8192 _14 flash program memory,368 bytes of RAM, 256 bytes of non-volatile EEPROM memory, 33 I/O pins, 8multiplexed A/D converters with 10-bits resolution, PWM generator, 3 timers, analogue capture and comparator circuit, USART and internal and external interrupt facilities.

Fig. 1 Conceptual scheme of the proposed system

ii) Display Unit (Liquid Crystal Display): Display unit used in our project will be Liquid crystal display (LCD) which makes our project user friendly by displaying everything on the display. Liquid crystal displays (LCD) are widely used in recent years as compared to LEDs or seven segment displays as LCD can be used to display alphanumeric as well as special characters. Also due to the declining prices of LCD, the ability to display numbers, characters and graphics, incorporation of a refreshing controller into the LCD, their by relieving the CPU of the task of refreshing the LCD and also the ease of programming for characters and graphics. The LCD, which is used as a display in our project, is LMB162A. The main features of this LCD are: 16 X 2 display, intelligent LCD, used for alphanumeric characters & based on ASCII codes. This LCD contains 16 pins, in which 8 pins are used as 8-bit data I/O, which are extended

ASCII. Three pins are used as control lines these are Read/Write pin, Enable pin and Register select pin. Two pins are used for Backlight and LCD voltage, another two pins are for Backlight & LCD ground and one pin is used for contrast change.

iii) Buzzer for Beep Source: A Buzzer will be used as an audio alarm here. A buzzer or beeper is an audio signaling device, which may be mechanical, electromechanical, or piezoelectric. The buzzer used in our project will be piezoelectric buzzer. Instead of this buzzer we can also use a musical IC with combination of speaker as an audio alarm for the same. The various musical ICs (like UM66) with different musical sounds are available.

iv) Relay Driver using Opt coupler (Auto Electro Switching): Relay is an electrically operated switch. The relay's switch connections are usually labeled COM, NC and COM = Common, always connect to the moving part of the switch. NC = Normally Closed, COM is connected to this when the relay coil is off. NO = Normally Open, COM is connected to this when the relay coil is on.

An **Auto Electro Switching/Relay Driver** circuit comprises of an opt coupler which will isolate the controller from the outer spikes or fluctuations or from the external hardware and at the same time it drives a power transistor i.e. make it on when a signal from the controller pin is applied to it. Opt coupler actually comprises of a diode and a phototransistor. It comes in a DIP IC package. Thus signal from the MCU is given to the LED part or the driving part. When LED begins to glow then the phototransistor acts as on switch or short circuit. This output is given to power transistor, which will amplify the current of the signal and then can be used to drive a relay. The I/P signal is connected to the Relay's "common" terminal and the O/P can be taken from the relay's "NO" terminal. When relay is ON then "NO" is connected to the "common" terminal of the relay.

v) Stepper Motor Drive using Opt coupler: The stepper motor is an electromagnetic device that converts digital pulses into mechanical shaft rotation. And it is used where some particular movement is required like in the application of barrier opening/closing, lift movement etc.

Stepper Motor Driver:

To excite any winding of stepper motor near about 50-100 mA current is required. But any I/O pin of any MCU can source/sink a current of near about 20 mA. So for its interfacing with microcontrollers a power or current amplifier circuit is required, known as motor driver circuits. Mainly two such driver circuits i.e. ULN2003 and transistor /opt couplers are often used. A Motor Driver circuit comprises of an opt coupler which will isolate the controller from the outer spikes or back EMF produced from the motor winding and at the same time it drives a power transistor i.e. make it on when a signal from the controller pin is applied to it. Opt coupler actually comprises of a diode and a phototransistor. It comes in a DIP IC package. Thus signal from the MCU is given to the LED part or the driving part. When LED begins to glow then the phototransistor acts as on switch or short circuit. This output is given to power transistor, which will amplify the current of the signal and then can be used to drive a motor winding.

vi) ZigBee Network: ZigBee is a wireless communication technology based on the IEEE 802.15.4 standard for communication among multiple devices in a wireless personal –area network (WPAN). ZigBee is designed to be more affordable than other WPANs (such as Bluetooth) in terms of costs and above all energy consumption.

A ZigBee personal –area network (ZBPAN) consist of at least one (or more) router(s). The network is created when a coordinator selects a channel and starts the communication, henceforth a router or an end device can join the network. The typical distance range of ZigBee transmission range, depending on the environment conditions and the transmission power, shifts tens to hundreds of meters ,and the transmission power is deliberately kept as low as possible (in the order of a few mill watts) to maintain the lowest energy consumption[3][4].

2. STREET LIGHTING SYSTEM

Power supplied by a battery is recharged by a solar panel during day time. The capacity of the battery depends up on the specific needs of the final application.

The right inclination and orientation of the solar panels is determined to enable the best outcome of the operation. It is possible to refer publication that provides the precise statistics as a function of latitude (denoting to UNI 10349 information acquired by PVGIS [27]). For the sizing of the

panel, it is essential to conclude the annual power essential to power lighting system under the region to be protected.

3. AUTOMATIC NUMBER PLATE RECOGNITION (ANPR)

ANPR is utilized to store images captured by the cameras as well as the text from the license plate with configurable to store a photograph of driver. Systems commonly use infrared lighting to allow the camera to take the picture at any time of the day [5-7]. ANPR technology tends to be reason specific, owing to plate variation from one place to another.

ANPR makes use of optical character recognition (OCR) on images taken by cameras. When Dutch vehicle registration plates were altered in 2002, one of the modifications done was to the font, presenting small gaps in some letters (such as P and R) to make the more distinct and therefore more legible to such systems. Some license plate arrangements use variation in font sizes and positioning –ANPR systems must be able to cope with such differences in directive to be efficiently operational. Further complex systems could cope with international variants, though many programs are exclusively designed for every nation.

The cameras utilized can comprise of existing road-rule enforcement or closed-circuit television cameras, as well as mobile which are usually attached to vehicles. Some systems use infrared cameras to take a clearer image of plate [7-16]

4. ACCESS CONTROL SECURITY SYSTEM

In the arena of physical security as well as data security ‘access control is a selective of access to a place or other resource [16]. This act of accessing may mean consuming, entering, or using. Permission to access a resource is called *authorization*. Locks and login credentials are to analogous mechanism of access control.

Access control system operation:

Once a credential is offered to the reader, the reader sends the credential’s data that is generally a number, to a control panel, an extremely consistent supercomputer. This control panel matches the credential’s data to an access control list, allows or rejects the offered application and transmits a transaction log to a databank. When the access is refused centered on the access control list, the door remains sealed. If a match is struck amongst the credential and the access

control list then the control panel maneuvers a stepper motor that, in turn, opens the door. There are three types (factors) of authenticating information [17]

- a. something the user knows e.g. a password, pass-phrase or PIN
- b. something the user has, such as smart card or a key fob
- c. something the user is, such as finger print, verified by biometric measurement

III RELATED WORK

Optical character recognition (OCR) is extensively utilized technique that transfigures scanned imageries of on paper text, handwritten text typescripts into machine coded text data like ASCII. The info data could be acknowledged printed characters as well as handwritten characters; however the performance is directly reliant on the quality of input data. The OCR performed offline. K.K. Kim, et. al., [18] is strictly designed for Korean plates. It has designed a system implementing for support vector machines as well as report striking average character recognition. M.A. Ko., et .al. [19], T. Naito, et. al., [20] presents peak optical character recognizers familiarized in a 2D-plane that are able to uphold high success average only contained by a restricted assortment of visual angle and shooting space.

IV PROPOSED ALGORITHM

The first step here is capturing the image approximately 1 meter from the number plate with camera. The purpose is to obtain a clean picture free of any distortion. Second stage is cropping the number plate from captured image.. The third step is character recognition in which the OCR technique is used to recognize the character. This cropped image will be the input for the character recognition. The fourth step is to operate stepper motor which is interfaced with microcontroller unit. Fifth step is to operate street light when required for this purpose, LDR is interfaced with MCU. The flow chart of presented work is given below.

FLOW CHART

REFERENCES

- [1] M.A.D. Costa , G.H. Costa, H.A. dos Santos, L. Schuch and J.R. Pinheiro, “ A high frequency autonomous street lighting system based on solar energy and LEDs” in Proc. Power Electron. Conf. Brazil, Oct. 1, 2009, pp. 265-273.
- [2] W.Yue, S. Changlong, Z. Xianglong and Y. Wei “Design of new intelligence street light control system .” in Proc. 8th IEEE Int. Conf. Control Autom , Jun,9-11-2010,pp. 1423-1427.
- [3] Max Stream Inc-802.15.4 and ZigBee 2006.
- [4] ZigBee Alliances, ZigBee specification overview, 2012. [online], available: <http://www.zigbee.org/specification/zigbee/overview.aspx>
- [5] “CCTV Network track “getaway car”. BBC News. 21 Nov, 2005, retrieved 2013 -08-12.
- [6] “Plate Recognition” on Photocop.com.
- [7] “Algorithm for License Plate Recognition”. VISL, Technion, 2002.
- [8] “A Real –time vehicle License Plate Recognition (LPR)”, VISL Technion, 2003.
- [9] “An Approach to License Plate Recognition”, University of Calgary, 1996, retrieved 2012-01-24.
- [10] Draghici and Sorin (1997), “ A neural network based artificial vision system for license plate recognition”(PDF). Dept. of computer, Wayne state University, retrieved 2012-01-24.
- [11] “License Plate Recognition in Turkey (Plaka Okuma Sistemi)”, Gremedia.com, retrieved 2012-01-24.
- [12] Kwasnicka, Halina, Wawrzyniak, Bartosz (2002), “License plate localization and Recognition in camera pictures”, AI-METH 2002-Artificial Intelligence Method November 13-15(Gliwice, Poland), retrieved 2014-01-13.
- [13] Kahraman, Fatih, Gokmen, Muhittin (2003), “License Plate Character Segmentation based on the Gabor Transform and Vector Quantization” on 2006-05-24, retrieved 2012-01-24.
- [14] Ondrej Martinsky, (2007), “Algorithmic and mathematical principles of Automatic number plate recognition systems”, Brno University of Technology, retrieved 2012-01-24.

- [15] “A License plate recognition algorithm for Intelligent Transportation system applications” University of the Aegean and National Technical University of Athens, 2006. Archived from the original on 2008-04-20, retrived 2012-01-24.
- [16] RFC 4949
- [17] Federal Financial Institution Examination Council, (2008), “Authentication in an Internet Banking Environment”, retrieved 2009-12-31.
- [18] K.K. Kim, K.I. Kim, J.B. Kim and H.J. Kim, “Learning –based approach for license plate recognition”, in Proc. IEEE signal Process, 2000, vol. 2, pp. 614 -623.
- [19] T. Naito, T. Tsukada, K. Yamda, K. Kozuka, and S. Yamamoto, “Robust License –Plate Recognition Method for passing vehicle under outside environment”, IEEE Trans. on Vehicular Technology, vol. 49, No. 46, November 2000, pp. 2309-2319.
- [20] M.A. Ko and Y.M. Kim, “License Plate Surveillance System Using Weighted Template Matching”, in Proc. Of the 32nd Applied Imagery Pattern Recognition Workshop, Oct. 2003, pp. 269 -274.